

LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL ANALYSIS OF LEXEMES EXPRESSING TRADITION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation. In this article we tried to illustrate linguocultural peculiarities and analysis of the lexical units representing Uzbek and English traditions, especially wedding ceremonies and traditions related to the birth of a baby, to shed light on their semantic nature and linguistic and cultural features, to identify their similarities and differences, and theoretically analyze them.

Key words: linguaculturology, tradition, custom, belief, origin of word

Annotatsiya. Biz ushbu maqolada o'zbek va ingliz an'analarini ifodalovchi lug'aviy birliklarning lingvomadaniy o'ziga xosliklarini ko'rsatib, tahlil qilishga, ayniqsa, to'y marosimlari va go'dak tug'ilishi bilan bog'liq urf-odatlarini ko'rsatishga, ularning semantik tabiati va lingvistik-madaniy xususiyatlarini yoritishga, o'xshashlik va farqlarni nazariy tahlil qilishga harakat qildik.

Kalit so'zlar: lingvakulturologiya, an'ana, odat, e'tiqod, so'zning kelib chiqishi

Аннотация: В этой статье мы анализируем лингводидактические особенности языковых единиц, выражающих узбекские и английские аналоги, особенности свадебных обрядов и обычаев, связанных с рождением ребенка, выявляем их семантическую природу и языково-культурные особенности, а также проводим теоретический анализ сходств и различий.

Ключевые слова: лингвакультурология, традиция, обычай, верование, происхождение слова.

The origins of linguocultural research can be traced back to Wilhelm von Humboldt, who believed that there is a connection and mutual accompaniment between cultural inventiveness and language formation. A. Wierzbickaya, R. M. Keesing, R. Langacker, V. Maslova, V. Karasic, S. Vorcacev, V. Telia, V. Shaklein, F. Vorobev, J. Stepanov, E. Levchenko, V. Kononenko, and V. Zhayvoronok are the scientists who put out the most effort in this field.

In Uzbek linguistics, there are several scientific works dedicated to the study of linguo-cultural studies, which are focused on a number of issues, such as the scientific foundation of linguistics and the reflection of culture in language. In particular, as examples of initial scientific research dedicated to linguo-cultural studies in Uzbekistan, linguist A. Nurmonov's "Linguo-cultural direction in the Uzbek language", N. Mahmudov's "Looking for ways of perfect study of the language", N. Sayidrahimova's "Scientific study of linguo-cultural studies" Some comments on the foundation of the language", "Components of Linguistic Culture", as well as D. Khudoyberganova's monograph on "Anthropocentric study of the text", "Annotated Dictionary of Uzbek Language Similes" can be cited as examples. In these studies, the issues of the essence, subject and object of the science of linguistic and cultural studies were studied. Because the communication behavior is an integral part of the character of the nation, they are closely related to each other

Linguistic and cultural analysis of lexemes expressing tradition in English and Uzbek languages involves examining the words and expressions used to convey traditional customs, practices, and beliefs in each language, as well as the cultural significance attached to these traditions.

Literary critic B. Sarimsakov divided the ceremonies into four groups in terms of subject and task:

"The first group - rituals based on the magical power of the lexeme: kinna, badik (gulafsho), burei - burei, avrash and curses, etc.

The second group is the ceremony of the children's period in the cradle: chilla, chilla, uyqu qochirish, beshikka solish.

The third group is wedding ceremonies: jar, yor-yor, olan, lapar, kelin salom, kuyov salom, to'y olqishlari, oyna ko'rsatar etc.

The fourth group is the mourning ceremony: yig'i-yo'qlovlar va motam yor-yorlari, etc. "

Wedding lexeme used only in a positive sense in the Uzbek language, and all its forms, especially "tug'ilish to'y", "beshik to'y", "chilla to'y", "sunnat to'y", "muchal to'y", "nikoh to'y", "payg'ambar to'y", "hoji to'y", "uy to'y", "moshina to'y" and similar are celebrated with joy, being presented with games and treats, and are symbolized by entertainment and fun.

While studying the research topic, based on the collected data, we can divide the lexemes representing wedding ceremonies into three groups:

1. Lexemes representing traditions on the eve of a wedding: sovchilik, oq kiydi, sepberdi, sarpoyig'ar, ko'rpahashar, fotiha to'y, unashtirish, qizbazmi.

2. Lexemes representing customs performed by the groom: kuyov o‘tirmadi, to‘nkiygizar, tovoqhaqi, kuyovqamar;

3. Lexemes representing customs in the groom’s house: yuzochdi, yuzochar, betochar, surpayoyar, un elatar, bol yatar, moy tomizar, kuyruqkesar, ota ko‘rdi, uchkunlik, kelinsalom.

Such ceremonies have their own lexeme or performance in different regions of Uzbekistan, and they are made up of examples of folk art. From the beginning to the end of the wedding, various forms of the folklore genre are used. In particular, prayers, advice, songs, proverbs and sayings are among them. So, wedding ceremonies include materials with the participation of ethnographic lexemes based on folklore.

In the matter of weddings, Great Britain has a lot of tradition and customs. Although not all of them are practiced in today’s modern world, they are not entirely forgotten. Each wedding is carried out in accordance with national values, but today the importance of using English wedding customs is not significant.

In English, lexemes expressing tradition include words such as "heritage, " "custom, " "ritual, " "legacy, " "folklore, " "ancestral, " "ritual, " and "cultural practice. " Each of these lexemes carries a specific nuance related to traditional aspects, such as the passing down of customs through generations, the importance of cultural practices, and the preservation of heritage.

The study of customs related to English folk wedding traditions, such as stag parties, stag nights, hen parties, traditional bridal entry song Giving away the bride Wedding vow and related ethnographic lexemes, provides specific information about the customs and traditions of the country. Some of these rituals are not carried out by English people living in other regions. This indicates the uniqueness of the local ethnographic lexical layer.

The common aspect of the lexeme of traditions related to the birth of a baby in Uzbek and English is that these two peoples, according to their religious beliefs and imagination, protect the baby from the evil eye, give it a long life, health and prosperous life is characterized by virtues such as desire.

In the ethnographic lexicon of the English and Uzbek languages, lexemes related to the birth of a baby form a large group. For this reason, in the lexical-semantic analysis, they are divided into two types - the lexicon related to the customs and traditions associated with the birth of a baby (azon chaqirish, cho‘qintirish, chilla saqlash, sovg‘a berish etc.) and it is appropriate to study the lexicon related to calling the baby by name, caressing, and putting him to sleep.

In conclusion, the study of lexical units in Uzbek and English languages is important not only for linguistics, but also for history and ethnography. After all, they express the uniqueness of these two languages, the past, lifestyle, cultural heritage, imagination and values of the Uzbek and English people who are the owners of these languages. And scientific research strengthens the evidence, opens the way to new views and discoveries. Linguistic and cultural analysis of lexemes expressing tradition in English and Uzbek languages provides insights into the values, beliefs, and practices that are integral to the cultural identity of the speakers of these languages.

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